

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Factors affecting the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals in inpatient unit: Literature review

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Abstract

Introduction: Patient safety is a condition where there is no danger that threatens the patient during the patient care process and the risk of harm is reduced. Infection prevention and control in inpatient units is a challenge because there are so many Adverse Events that occur in them. Objective: To Determine the factors that influence or hinder the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals in inpatient unit. Method: Using the literature review method. Article searches were carried out through the Garuda Portal database and Google Scholar using the keywords patient safety, patient safety goals, inpatient units. In total, 5 research results obtained articles that met the inclusion criteria. Result: Based on the results of a review of 5 articles showing that several factors that influence or hinder the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals inpatient unit are age, knowledge, work environment, and supervision, as well as attitudes and motivation of health workers. Conclusion: Factors that influence the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals in inpatient unit are influenced by 3 important factors: individual factors, organizational factors, and psychological factors.

Keywords: Patient Safety; Patient Safety Goals; Inpatient Unit

1. Introduction

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines patient safety as the absence of danger that threatens the patient during the patient care process and reducing the risk of danger occurring in health services to the minimum acceptable danger (1). Patient safety is a basic principle of health services throughout the world (2). The goal of patient safety in health services is very important, namely to protect patients from risks that can arise during the health care process (3). The views of several developed countries have undergone a change from initially being based on the paradigm of "quality" now to "quality safety" meaning that apart from the importance of improving the quality of service, what is more important is continuously maintaining patient safety. Patient safety is one of the most important indicators in the quality of hospital services, so patient safety requires very good management so that hospitals can provide quality services (4). Based on Minister of Health No. 11 of 2017 concerning patient safety, patient safety is a system that aims to make patients safer. In creating optimal patient safety, patient safety have 6 goals namely patient identification, increasing effective communication, ensuring the safety of medications that must be taken into account, ensuring correct medical procedures, correct techniques and appropriate procedures, reducing the risk of infection due to health care, and reducing the risk of patient injury due to falls (5).

Problems related to patient safety occur in hospitals throughout the world. A study in America from the Institute of Medicine or IOM stated that medical errors currently cause 250,000 deaths every year and are the third cause of death after cancer and heart disease (Permenkes, 2017). Apart from that, IOM also reported that in 1999 as many as 44,000-98,000 patients died due to service errors during patient hospitalization and caused by safety accidents. According to this study, safety accidents were caused by a lack of safety management (42.1%) (6). In contrast to the research

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previously presented, based on the Patient Safety Committee report in Indonesia, the number of adverse events is relatively small, namely in 2009 there were 144 incidents, in 2019 there were 103 incidents, and in 2011 there were 34. Even though in reality it is more than that, it's just that not all adverse events incidents are reported (7). Adverse events that occur during the provision of health services are thought to be the main cause of morbidity and mortality. This strengthens the important role of health facilities in providing quality and safe health services at the global health level (8). In line with the strategic objective in the WHO Global Patient Safety Action Plan, namely "Creating patient safety that has no danger (zero danger) and if the provision of health care poses a danger to the patient, this can be avoided wherever the health service is provided" (9).

The inpatient unit is a unit that has complexity within it. Many adverse events can occur while a patient is hospitalized. The incidence of nosocomial infections or healthcare associated infections (HAIs) is a problem in Indonesia and even in the world. The prevalence of nosocomial infections that occur in inpatient units worldwide reaches 1.4 million or 9%. In Indonesia itself, the number of nosocomial infections is quite high, namely 6-16%. Phelebitis is an infection that has the highest incidence rate in government and private hospitals with a total of 2,168 patients occurring out of a total of 124,733 patients at risk (10). The incidence of nosocomial infections indicates a decline in the quality of medical services, resulting in long patient care, large health service costs, and resulting in high morbidity and mortality rates. Inpatient units are a measure of the quality of hospital services. If there are minimal incidents of adverse events, it can be said that the quality of the hospital is also good (11). Infection Prevention and Control (PPI) is very necessary to reduce the risk of transmission of microorganisms from both known and unknown sources (12). Based on Minister of Health Regulation Number 8 of 2015 concerning anti- microbial resistance control programs in hospitals, it is stated that PPI is one of the most important elements that must be present in hospitals. The implementation of the PPI program is considered not optimal because there are still many incidents of nosocomial infections occurring and the target has not been achieved as expected. (13)

Based on the data obtained, it appears that many adverse events occur due to a lack of optimal implementation of patient safety goals. The implementation of patient safety targets in inpatient units is sometimes considered less than optimal because it is influenced by several factors and causes a high incidence of adverse events, one of which is a high number of cases of nosocomial infections or healthcare associated infections (HAIs). Infection prevention and control in inpatient units is a challenge. Apart from maintaining the quality of service, it is also to maintain the safety of patients in the hospital. Factors that can cause nosocomial infections can be caused by individual factors (from health workers themselves), organizational factors, and psychological factors. Cases of nosocomial infections will not occur if health workers and health service providers pay close attention to these aspects. Therefore, the author focuses on the fifth patient safety goals in inpatient, namely reducing the risk of infection due to health care in inpatient units. The author wants to analyze the factors that influence the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals in inpatient units.

2. Material and methods

The method used by the author in compiling this article is literature review. Method literature review is the process of reading, obtaining, finding, and evaluating research. The preparation of articles is carried out by selecting, reading and analyzing study materials that are relevant to the topic discussed, namely the factors that influence the implementation of patient safety targets in inpatient units. By reading several reading sources related to the study material, carrying out an analysis prepared in your own sentences and language and then writing it down to complete the entire discussion of this article. Data collection was carried out through the Garuda Portal and Google Scholar. Keywords used in article searches are: patient safety, patient safety goals, And inpatient unit. The reading sources or related references used in preparing this article have the inclusion criteria of being published in the last 5 years or no later than 2019 to no later than 2024. The articles used are original article, full text, And open access. The selection of articles was based on the purpose of writing, namely to find out factors that could influence or hinder the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals inpatient units.

3. Results and discussion

Based on the search results, 5 articles were obtained with studies conducted in 5 hospitals in Indonesia. There is two article published in 2019, two article published in 2020, one articles published in 2022. Of the 5 selectec articles, 3 of them were published on Google Scholar and 2 of them were published on Portal Garuda.

The research results show that each hospital has factors that can influence or hinder the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals in inpatient. Factors that influence the implementation of the program are grouped into individual factors, organizational factors and psychological factors. Based on the results of the review, it was found that every

nurse in the hospital had implemented patient safety. The research results show that each hospital has factors that can influence or hinder the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals in inpatient unit. Factors that influence the implementation of the program are grouped into individual factors, organizational factors and psychological factors.

Table 1 List of Articles

No.	Author	Research Title	Method	Result
1.	Dewi, et al. [14]	Analysis of the Implementation of the Patient Safety Program in the Inpatient Unit of Wawa Husada Hospital, Malang Regency	The research uses qualitative methods with a descriptive approach	Factors that hinder the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals are forgetfulness due to nurses' workload. In reducing infections related to health services, hospitals do this by washing hands and using PPE. Nurses know how to reduce the risk of infection, but not all nurses remember and implement hand washing. Nurses forget because of the workload they receive.
2.	Handayani, et al. [15]	The Relationship between Characteristics, Knowledge and Motivation of Nurses with Hand Washing Compliance in the Inpatient Room at RSU Surya Husadha Denpasar	Researchers used quantitative methods with descriptive research type with a cross-sectional design	Factors related to the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals are age characteristics ($p=0.007$, $PR= 3.68$), level of education ($p=0.021$, $PR= 0.33$), knowledge ($p=.003$, $PR= 4.16$) and motivation ($p=0.013$).
3.	Mukhlis & Isnaini, et al. [16]	Factors Associated with the Implementation of Patient Safety Targets among Nurses in the Inpatient Installation of Langsa City Regional General Hospital	Researchers used quantitative analytical methods with a cross sectional design	Factors related to the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals are poor supervision, 97.7% with a P-value = 0.000, meaning there is a relationship. As many as 79.9% of respondents had an unfavorable and negative attitude in implementing patient targets with P-value = 0.001, meaning there is a relationship. As many as 47.9% of respondents had a high workload with a P-value of 0.003, meaning there is a relationship between workload and the implementation of patient safety targets.
4.	Alfian, et al. [17]	Factors Associated with the Implementation of Patient Safety Targets 1, 3, and 5 by Nurses in the Inpatient Room at Cahya Kawaluyan Hospital, Regency	Researchers used quantitative analytical methods with a cross sectional approach.	Factors related to the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals are knowledge ($p 0.006$), work motivation ($p 0.015$), work environment ($p 0.0001$), and teamwork ($p 0.001$).
5.	Sholikhah, et al [18]	The Relationship between Nurses' Knowledge and Attitudes with the Implementation of Patient Safety in Inpatients at PKU Muhammadiyah Sekapuk Hospital	Researchers used quantitative analytical methods with a cross sectional approach.	The factor related to the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals is the nurse's attitude with a value of $p = 0.039$, meaning it shows a relationship

3.1. Individual Factors

Individual factors or personal factors are elements that arise from a person's characteristics that influence social interactions and individual behavior. Individual factors of nurses as implementers patient safety have a significant influence on its implementation. The research results show that a positive mindset at work, especially in preventing hospital infections through correct hand washing practices, is influenced by a person's age (15). Knowledge factors

which include length of time working and education are also individual factors that can influence the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals. Length of time working and education can influence the level of knowledge of nurses. Knowledge and education are factors that can influence the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals in inpatient unit. According to Alfian's research results, knowledge is one of the factors that can influence the implementation of SKP 5 (17)

The workload experienced by implementing nurses has a significant impact on the implementation or failure to achieve patient safety goals. The higher the workload faced by executive nurses, the more difficult it is for them to meet patient safety goals due to time constraints. On the other hand, at a low workload, executive nurses tend to be better at implementing patient safety goals because they have flexibility in working time (16). This is in line with research conducted by Dewi which stated that although the majority of nurses have knowledge about how to reduce the risk of infection, not all staff always remember and implement hand washing. Nurses forget because they are often in a rush to carry out other work and forget to clean their hands (14). Therefore, the workload factor received by nurses has a significant effect on the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals.

3.2. Organizational Factors

Organizational factors or organizational culture are factors that influence individual and group actions in an organization, and have an impact on organizational systems and structures. The organization referred to here is a hospital. The implementation of SKP 5 has not yet gone completely well due to organizational factors including work environment conditions and supervision/supervisors. Work environment factors have a significant influence on the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals program in inpatient units. The work environment is considered good or suitable when people can carry out activities optimally, maintaining health, safety and comfort. The impact of work environment suitability can be seen over a long period of time. On the other hand, a poor work environment requires workers to require more time and effort, and does not support the achievement of an efficient work system design. Therefore, achieving the fifth patient safety goals is also influenced by a good work environment (17).

Based on research conducted by Mukhlis & Isnaini, it is stated that there is a relationship between supervision and the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals patient safety targets. With good supervision, nurses tend to carry out patient safety targets well (16). However, it is also important to remember that the responsibility for implementing patient safety goals actually lies with each implementing nurse when providing nursing care. Supervision can encourage and motivate nurses to implement of the fifth patient safety goals.

3.3. Psychological Factors

Psychological factors include the attitudes and motivation of health workers. A positive attitude from health workers is needed to speed up patient recovery because this attitude can improve the healing process. Lack of quality in treating the pain experienced by patients can result in errors handling problems that occur in patients in hospitals. Nurses who have a positive nature will feel responsible for the patient's recovery so they try as hard as possible to implement SKP 5 (18). According to Mukhlis & Isnaini's research, attitude has a significant influence on the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals. Nurses with negative attitudes tend to face obstacles in implementing patient safety targets due to lack of patience, non-compliance and lack of responsibility. This can influence their performance to be less satisfactory (16).

The next factor is the motivation factor. The results of research conducted by Alfian stated that compliance with hand washing is an example of a habit or behavior that is carried out repeatedly, and individual motivation is an important factor in shaping nurses' hand washing compliance behavior. This is also in line with research conducted by Handayani which states that motivation is a condition that can inspire someone to focus on achieving work goals (15). Therefore, motivation factors have a significant influence on the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals.

4. Conclusion

This research concludes that the factors that can influence or hinder 5 in the inpatient unit can be grouped into 3 factors, namely individual factors, organizational factors, and psychological factors. Individual factors include the age of health workers, knowledge, length of work and education of health workers, and the workload received by inpatient unit health workers which causes them to forget to apply hand hygiene according to SOP. Meanwhile, organizational factors that can influence or hinder the implementation of the fifth patient safety goals include a work environment that does not support health workers in implementing the fifth patient safety goals and poor supervision/supervision of health workers. Psychological factors that influence are the attitude of medical personnel in implementing the correct hand washing steps and the individual's minimal motivation regarding washing hands after or before carrying out medical

procedures.

Compliance with ethical standards

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